

Ammino-OPEs Glycosides and Blue light: a powerful synergy in Photodynamic therapy

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Supplementary material

¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra

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Absorption and emission spectra

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Fig. S1. ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz) of compound **7a** in CDCl_3 . The reference signal of chloroform is set to $\delta = 7.26$ ppm.

Fig. S2. ^{13}C NMR spectrum (500 MHz) of compound **7a** in CDCl_3 . The reference signal of chloroform is set to $\delta = 77.0$ ppm.

Fig. S3. ¹H NMR spectrum (500 MHz) of compound **7b** in CDCl₃. The reference signal of chloroform is set to $\delta = 7.26$ ppm.

Fig. S4. ¹³C NMR spectrum (500 MHz) of compound **7a** in CDCl₃. The reference signal of chloroform is set to $\delta = 77.0$ ppm.

Fig. S5. ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz) of compound **10a** in CDCl_3 . The reference signal of chloroform is set to $\delta = 7.26$ ppm.

Fig. S6. ^{13}C NMR spectrum (500 MHz) of compound **7a** in CDCl_3 . The reference signal of chloroform is set to $\delta = 77.0$ ppm.

Fig. S7. ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz) of compound **10b** in CDCl_3 . The reference signal of chloroform is set to $\delta = 7.26$ ppm.

Fig. S8. ^{13}C NMR spectrum (500 MHz) of compound **7a** in CDCl_3 . The reference signal of chloroform is set to $\delta = 77.0$ ppm.

Fig. S9. ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz) of compound **2** OPE-Mannose in dms0-d_6 . The reference signal of dimethylsulfoxide is set to $\delta = 2.49$ ppm.

Fig. S10. ^{13}C NMR spectrum (500 MHz) of compound **2** OPE-Mannose in dms0-d_6 . The reference signal of dimethylsulfoxide is set to $\delta = 39.5$ ppm.

Fig. S11. ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz) of compound **3** OPE-Maltose in dms0-d_6 . The reference signal of dimethylsulfoxide is set to $\delta = 2.49$ ppm.

Fig. S10. ^{13}C NMR spectrum (500 MHz) of compound **3** OPE-Maltose in dms0-d_6 . The reference signal of dimethylsulfoxide is set to $\delta = 39.5$ ppm.

Fig. S11. Absorption (epsilon) and emission spectra of **1 OPE-Glucose**, **2 OPE-Mannose** and **3 OPE-Maltose** in dichloromethane.

Fig. S12. Absorption and emission spectra of **1 OPE-Glucose**, **2 OPE-Mannose** and **3 OPE-Maltose** in aqueous solution